

Supplementary Figure 1. Structural comparison of the gut microbiota at the genus level between depressant-like mice without (no KPs) and with KPs treatment. Mean relative abundances of the genera *Anaerostipes*, *Romboutsia*, *Oscillibacter* and *Alistipes*. Compared with the KPs-untreated depressant-like group, these bacterial genera were inhibited (*Anaerostipes* and *Romboutsia*,) or enriched (*Oscillibacter* and *Alistipes*) in the KPs-treated group. The data are presented as means \pm SD ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical significances are indicated by asterisks ($*P < 0.05$).